

TEACHERS' BELIEFS AND PRACTICES OF SOCIAL AND EMOTIONAL LEARNING: IMPLICATIONS ON KINDERGARTNERS' ENGAGEMENT IN MULTI-GRADE CLASSES IN INDIGENOUS PEOPLES EDUCATION (IPED) SCHOOLS

Jerelyne C. Doncillo, LPT

Lourdes College, Cagayan DE Oro City, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15332584>

ABSTRACT

In the context of inclusive and culturally responsive early childhood education, fostering Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) has become increasingly essential, especially in diverse and multi-grade classrooms. This study investigates the relationship between kindergarten teachers' beliefs and practices in Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) and the cognitive, affective, and behavioral engagement of kindergartners in multi-grade Indigenous Peoples Education (IPED) classrooms in Agusan del Sur, Philippines. Grounded in Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory, the study highlights the importance of teacher guidance and social interaction in early childhood education, especially in culturally diverse and multi-grade settings. A descriptive-correlational research design was used, involving 60 teachers and 300 kindergartners. Data were collected through validated survey questionnaires assessing teachers' SEL beliefs and practices and pupils' engagement levels. Ethical protocols, such as informed consent and data confidentiality, were strictly followed. The findings revealed that teachers had very high beliefs and high practices in SEL, indicating a strong commitment to fostering a supportive learning environment. Kindergartners exhibited high engagement, particularly in affective and behavioral domains. Statistical analysis using Spearman's Rho showed a significant positive relationship between teachers' SEL beliefs and kindergartners' affective and behavioral engagement, but no significant correlation with cognitive engagement. Furthermore, teachers' SEL practices were significantly linked only to affective engagement. Additionally, the study emphasizes the critical role of culturally responsive SEL practices, highlighting the need for tailored strategies that align with the cultural

context of Indigenous students. The study concludes that while teachers' SEL beliefs and practices positively influence emotional and behavioral engagement, further support is needed to enhance cognitive engagement in multi-grade IPED classrooms.

Keywords: *Social and Emotional Learning, kindergartners engagement, multi-grade, Indigenous Education, kindergarten, Teachers Beliefs and Practices.*

INTRODUCTION

Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) has become a fundamental part of the early childhood education, facilitating children develop basic life skills along academic knowledge. In fostering self-awareness, emotional control, and strong interpersonal relationships, SEL supports early childhood learners in guiding both inside the classroom and in the real-world setting (CASEL, 2019). Research shows that when children receive consistent support in SEL, they manage to perform better inside the classroom, build positive relationships, and develop a stronger emotional resilience (Jones et al., 2020). Teachers play a key role in this process, as their help creates the foundation for emotionally supportive and engaging learning environments (Brackett et al., 2019).

Although SEL is widely recognized for its benefits, many of the existing researches focuses mainly on student outcomes, overlooking the role of teachers in shaping and implementing SEL practices (McClelland et al., 2017; Goldstein 2023). According to the studies teachers' beliefs, attitudes, and training play a crucial role in how Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) is implemented in the classroom. When teachers genuinely believe in the benefits of SEL, they are more likely to integrate it into their daily teaching, creating a more supportive and engaging learning environment for students (Lavigne et al., 2021). However, having positive beliefs alone is not enough adequate training and professional development help teachers feel confident and equipped to apply SEL strategies effectively (Collie et al., 2022). The schools that prioritize SEL training and cultivate a strong SEL environment manage to see better student results, including improved emotional well-being and classroom behavior (Schonert-Reichl, 2023). These findings highlight the need for ongoing teacher support and professional development to ensure that SEL is not just an idea inside the head, but a meaningful practice that benefits a teachers and pupils.

Additionally, many SEL initiatives focus on improving student engagement without even fully considering how the program affects teachers' instructional practices over time (McClelland et al., 2017; Goldstein 2023). White et al. (2020) highlight the importance of understanding how teachers perceive and apply SEL in multi-grade classrooms, particularly in Indigenous communities where the learning environment is entirely different from a normal mono grade classroom.

Furthermore, this study seeks to explore how teachers' beliefs and practices regarding SEL influence kindergartners' engagement in multi-grade IPED schools. By examining this relationship, the research seeks to provide insights into effective strategies for integrating SEL in culturally diverse and limited classroom environment. Ultimately, the findings of this study will contribute to the development of more inclusive, responsive, and

evidence-based teaching practices that support the overall well-being and learning experiences of an early childhood education in Indigenous communities.

This research, therefore focuses on teachers teaching multi-grade classrooms in Filipino kindergartners, specifically children aged 5–7 years old, in Indigenous Peoples Education (IPED) schools. It seeks to understand how teachers' beliefs and classroom practices shape young learners' social and emotional growth, particularly in cognitive, affective and behavioral not just only looking at teaching strategies, this research also considers the unique cultural and environmental factors that influence both how teachers implement SEL and how students engage in learning. In exploring the influence, the study hopes to offer valuable insights that can help strengthen SEL programs in diverse, multi-grade classrooms. Finally, the goal is to provide practical recommendations that support teachers in creating a more nurturing and effective learning environment for young children.

Research Questions

This study intends to determine the relationship of Social and Emotional Learning with the kindergarten teachers' performance in the IPED multi-grade schools in the Division of Agusan del Sur.

Specifically, it aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the participants' self-report of their beliefs on Social and Emotional Learning?
2. What is the participants' assessment of their practices on Social and Emotional Learning?
3. What is the kindergartners' level of engagement in terms of the following dimensions:
 - 3.1. Cognitive;
 - 3.2. Affective; and
 - 3.3. behavioral?
4. Are the teachers' beliefs and practices of Social and Emotional Learning significantly associated with their kindergartners' engagement?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive-correlational (Spearman's Rho) method to identify connections between teachers' SEL beliefs, practices, and learners' engagement levels. The study was conducted in multi-grade classes in the Division of Agusan del Sur, Philippines, involving sixty (60) teachers, who were teaching kindergarten, grade 1 and 2 teachers and Three hundred (300) kindergartners from multi-grade IPED schools selected through partial enumeration due to the challenging and high-risk conditions of the research area. Data collection was done through a survey questionnaire, focusing on the self-assessment of the teacher about SEL, their practices on SEL and measuring three domains of kindergartners engagement: cognitive, affective, and behavioral.

The survey instrument was validated through expert review to ensure clarity, relevance, and alignment with the study's objectives. Based on feedback, some items were revised. A pilot test with teachers outside the study area assessed reliability, with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.85, indicating high internal consistency. Participants were informed about the study's purpose, and informed consent was obtained from teachers, school administrators, and parents. Confidentiality was maintained by anonymizing responses.

Descriptive statistics such as mean, frequency, percentage distribution, and standard deviation were used in computing the data of each variables. Correlation Spearman' was used to determine the relationship between teachers' SEL beliefs, practices, and kindergartners' engagement.

RESULTS

Based on the data gathered, the following are the salient findings revealed in this study:

1. Teachers generally exhibited very high beliefs about Social and Emotional Learning indicating a strong recognition and commitment to integrating SEL strategies.
2. As a whole, teachers highly practiced Social and Emotional Learning, implying that they prioritize the emotional and social well-being of their pupils, and consistently integrate SEL strategies into their classroom environments.
3. Overall, the kindergartners' engagement in SEL Activities was reported to be *high* indicating that can generally relate SEL concepts to real-life situations, Social and Emotional Learning and can stay focused during SEL activities, showing attentiveness and active participation.
4. Teachers' beliefs in Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) had a significant positive relationship with kindergartners' affective and behavioral engagement, but no significant association with their cognitive or overall engagement.
5. Teachers' implementation of social and emotional learning (SEL) practices demonstrated a statistically significant positive relationship solely with learners' affective engagement, while no significant associations were found with cognitive, behavioral, or overall engagement.

DISCUSSION

Table 1 presents the frequency, percentage and mean distribution of the participants' self-report of their beliefs on social and emotional learning (SEL). Data show that they have rated their beliefs on SEL as generally very high (M=4.61) indicating that teachers have a strong belief in the importance of SEL in the classroom. This result is consistent with previous research showing that socioemotional competency among teachers has a major impact on student engagement and enhances learning outcomes (Gebre et al., 2025).

Research Question 1. What is the participants' self-report of their beliefs on Social and Emotional Learning?

Table 1

Frequency, Percentage and Mean Distribution of the Participants' Self-report of their Beliefs on Social and Emotional Learning

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	33	55.00
3.51-4.50	High	27	45.00
2.51-3.50	Moderate	0	0.00
1.51-2.50	Low	0	0.00
1.00-1.50	Very Low	0	0.00
Total		60	100.0
Overall Mean		4.61	
Interpretation		Very High	
SD		0.29	

Table 2 presents the frequency, percentage, and mean distribution of the participants' self-assessment of their practices in Social and Emotional Learning activities. The teachers highly evaluate their SEL activities as effective and incorporated into their teaching techniques, as indicated by the total mean score of 4.69 (SD=0.34), which is classified as "Very High." The majority of the participants said that their SEL practices were in the "Very High" range (4.51-5.00), and all participants gave their practices positive evaluations, with none falling into the "Low" or "Very Low" categories. These results imply that teachers are highly confident in their ability to use SEL strategies in the classroom. A phenomenological research of Roberts (2022) looked at teachers' experiences putting social-emotional learning (SEL) into practice. According to the results, teachers actively incorporate SEL into their lessons and acknowledge its importance, demonstrating a strong belief in its benefits for students' growth.

Research Question 2. What is the participants' assessment of their practices on Social and Emotional Learning?

Table 2

Frequency, Percentage and Mean Distribution of the Participants' Assessment of their Practices on Social and Emotional Learning

Range	Interpretation	Frequency	Percentage
4.51-5.00	Very High	39	65.00
3.51-4.50	High	21	35.00
2.51-3.50	Moderate	0	0.00

1.51-2.50	Low	0	0.00
1.00-1.50	Very Low	0	0.00
Total		60	100.0
Overall Mean		4.69	
Interpretation		Very High	
SD		0.34	

Table 3 summarizes the overall level of engagement in Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) across three dimensions Cognitive, Affective, and Behavioral among kindergartners. The data indicate a generally high level of engagement across all dimensions, with mean scores of 4.46 (Cognitive), 4.44 (Affective), and 4.48 (Behavioral), and an overall mean of 4.46. These results suggest that kindergartners are highly engaged in SEL, with consistent positive involvement in the cognitive, emotional, and behavioral aspects of learning. The high mean scores across all factors indicate that kindergartners are actively and positively engaged in SEL activities, with strong cognitive, emotional, and behavioral engagement. These findings emphasize the effectiveness of SEL programs in supporting young children's holistic development.

Research Question 3. What is the kindergartners' level of engagement in terms of the following dimensions: Cognitive; Affective; and Behavioral?

Table 3
Summary Table of Level of Engagement

Dimensions of Level of Engagement	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Cognitive	4.46	High	0.38
Affective	4.44	High	0.38
Behavioral	4.48	High	0.39
Overall Level of Engagement	4.46	High	0.23

Table 4 presents the results of Spearman's Rho correlation analysis examining the relationship between teachers' beliefs in Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) and kindergartners' engagement across four dimensions—cognitive, affective, behavioral, and overall engagement—in multi-grade Indigenous Peoples Education (IPED) classroom settings.

The findings reveal that affective engagement ($r = .154, p = .008$) and behavioral engagement ($r = .119, p = .040$) are positively and significantly associated with teachers' beliefs in SEL. In the context of multi-grade classrooms, where learners of varying developmental stages and learning needs coexist, these findings underscore the importance of teacher beliefs in fostering emotional safety and behavior regulation. A positive belief in SEL may encourage teachers to create warm, responsive, and inclusive environments, which are especially critical in IPED schools where cultural sensitivity and emotional security are central to student well-being and participation.

The results suggest that when teachers value SEL, they are more likely to model empathy, build positive relationships, and manage classroom dynamics effectively key strategies that help younger children in multi-grade circumstances feel emotionally supported and behave appropriately despite the complexity of shared instruction.

Conversely, cognitive engagement ($r = -.063, p = .274$) and overall engagement ($r = .100, p = .085$) did not yield statistically significant results. This may be attributed to the inherent challenges in multi-grade teaching, such as differentiated instruction, varied readiness levels, and limited instructional time, which could be associated with students' ability to sustain deep cognitive engagement. While SEL beliefs can improve emotional and behavioral aspects, their direct influence on cognitive involvement might be diluted by logistical and instructional constraints in such learning environments.

Given these results, the null hypothesis (H_{01}) is partially rejected. Teachers' beliefs in SEL show significant associations with affective and behavioral engagement, but not with cognitive or overall engagement. These findings highlight the unique role SEL beliefs play in supporting emotional and behavioral development in diverse and culturally rich multi-grade IPED classrooms, where fostering connection, cooperation, and emotional resilience is just as essential as academic instruction.

Research Question 4. Are the teachers' beliefs and practices of Social and Emotional Learning significantly associated with their kindergartners' engagement?

***H₀₁*. Teachers' beliefs of Social and Emotional Learning are not significantly associated with kindergartners' engagement.**

***H₀₂*: Teachers' practices of Social and Emotional Learning are not significantly associated with kindergartners' engagement.**

Table 4

Correlation (Spearman's Rho) Results of Beliefs in Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) with their Kindergartners Engagement

Teaching Engagement	Measures	Beliefs in SEL
Cognitive Engagement	Correlation Coefficient Sig. (2-tailed)	-.063 .274
Affective Engagement	Correlation Coefficient Sig. (2-tailed)	.154** .008
Behavioral Engagement	Correlation Coefficient Sig. (2-tailed)	.119* .040

Overall Engagement	Correlation Coefficient	.100
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.085

Table 5 presents the Spearman's Rho correlation analysis results examining the relationship between teachers' Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) practices and the level of kindergartners' engagement across four dimensions: cognitive, affective, behavioral, and overall engagement.

In the unique context of multi-grade IPED classrooms, where teachers simultaneously manage learners of different grade levels, abilities, and cultural backgrounds, the results highlight a positive finding: only affective engagement ($r = .141$, $p = .015$) has a significant positive correlation with teachers' SEL practices. This suggests that when teachers consistently implement SEL strategies like emotional check-ins, modeling empathy, and fostering supportive relationships kindergartners tend to feel more emotionally connected and safe within the learning environment. Such emotional security is particularly vital in multi-grade schools, where young learners must adapt to mixed-age interactions, shifting instructional focus, and complex social dynamics.

However, cognitive engagement ($r = .070$, $p = .224$), behavioral engagement ($r = -.076$, $p = .191$), and overall engagement ($r = .055$, $p = .340$) did not show statistically significant associations with SEL practices. This may be due to several factors inherent in multi-grade classrooms, such as limited individualized academic support, varying curriculum levels, or the overwhelming demands on teachers balancing multiple instructional topics. While SEL practices may foster emotional readiness, they might not be sufficient on their own to enhance deeper thinking, task focus, or consistent classroom behaviors in such complex learning environments.

As only the affective domain yielded a significant relationship, the null hypothesis (H_0) is partially retained. While teachers' SEL practices are positively and significantly associated with kindergartners' affective engagement, they are not significantly related to cognitive, behavioral, or overall engagement. These results imply that while SEL can create a nurturing emotional climate in multi-grade settings, its influence on academic thinking and behavioral consistency may require reinforcement through differentiated instructional strategies and behavior management tools tailored for diverse learner groups.

Table 5

Correlation (Spearman's Rho) Results of Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) Practices with their Kindergartners Engagement

Teaching Engagement	Measures	SEL Practices
Cognitive	Correlation Coefficient	.070
Engagement	Sig. (2-tailed)	.224
Affective	Correlation Coefficient	.141*
Engagement	Sig. (2-tailed)	.015

Behavioral Engagement	Correlation Coefficient	-.076
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.191
Overall Engagement	Correlation Coefficient	.055
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.340

In summary, while teachers' beliefs and practices in SEL show weak significant correlations with affective engagement and limited correlations with behavioral engagement, teachers' beliefs and practices in SEL were not determined to be significant in their association on cognitive engagement and overall student engagement. This inability to reject the null hypothesis means that while these results indicate a positive effect of SEL on learners' emotional engagement and some behavior responses, it appears that the effect does not hold much strength when assessed in the light of cognitive participation and generalized engagement, particularly when considered in the variable context of multigrade classrooms.

According to Zins et al. (2020), SEL contributes strongly to students' emotional regulation and interpersonal competencies, positively enhancing classroom affective and behavioral engagement. The connection, however, appears to differ in temporal sequence and thereby offers an indirect pathway leading to cognitive outcomes. Such an indirect connection may be mediated by other intervening variables such as instructional quality and properties of the wider classroom context. This was consistent with present findings showing that teachers' beliefs and practices in SEL were significantly associated with affective and behavioral engagement but did not display a statistically significant relationship with cognitive engagement.

Conclusions

The study underscores the pivotal role of teachers in advancing Social and Emotional Learning (SEL) within multigrade Indigenous Peoples Education (IPED) classrooms. Their strong convictions and consistent efforts in implementing SEL principles reflect a deep commitment to fostering learners' emotional well-being and prosocial behaviors. This supportive classroom climate appears to nurture a learning environment where young children feel emotionally safe and socially connected—conditions that are essential for meaningful participation and holistic development in diverse and layered educational settings.

Anchored in Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory, these findings reinforce the centrality of social interaction, guided support, and culturally responsive teaching in promoting learning. Vygotsky emphasized that development is mediated through the presence of a "more knowledgeable other," and in this context, the teacher serves as a critical scaffold for learners navigating complex social and emotional experiences. The observed learning dynamics resonate with the concept of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), where children thrive when instructional support is attuned to their evolving capacities. The emotional responsiveness and behavioral consistency facilitated by teachers affirm that learning is not solely cognitive but deeply social in nature. Thus, the study lends empirical support to the relevance of sociocultural theory in enhancing learner engagement—

particularly in multi-grade, culturally rich classroom environments like those found in IPED schools.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the researcher presents the following recommendations:

1. School Administrators that they:
 - 1.1. may strengthen the integration of SEL into early childhood education programs, particularly in multi-grade settings; and
 - 1.2. may provide necessary resources to support teachers in multi-grade IPED schools in implementing SEL activities.
2. The kindergarten teachers may undergo continuous professional development on SEL strategies to reinforce pupils' engagement.
3. Future researchers may explore other variables, such as parental involvement or classroom climate, to better understand the influence of SEL in early childhood education, especially in multigrade IPED settings.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study adhered to strict, ethical imperatives upheld by the LCREC. All participating teachers gave their informed consent prior to data collection. Participants received a thorough explanation of the study's goals, methods, and any ramifications, with a focus on their voluntary involvement and their freedom to discontinue participation at any moment without facing any repercussions before administering the survey questionnaire, ensuring that teachers fully understood the nature of their involvement.

The study made sure that participants were treated fairly and that the results were presented objectively, free from prejudice or discrimination to respect the values of beneficence and justice. Transparency and respect for the teachers and the schools involved were promoted by providing teachers with an easily readable overview of the findings. The welfare of teachers and students was the top concern during the entire research procedure.

Acknowledgments

The researcher is genuinely grateful to the number of individuals whose expertise, encouragement, and support have been fundamental to the success of this study:

First and foremost, she is and will be forever grateful to the Almighty God, for His countless blessings and guidance throughout this journey. His wisdom and strength have been her anchor during challenging times and His grace has enabled her to see the success of this study. Hence, she is truly grateful for His divine intervention that sustained her throughout the Graduate School journey;

Dr. Maria Alona A. Galendez whose guidance and insights have been invaluable throughout this journey. Her patience and expertise helped the researcher navigate complex challenges and inspired her to push the boundaries of her capabilities;

To the panel members; Dr. Kriscentti Exzur Barcelona, the Chair of the Thesis Committee and to the members of the panel: Dr. Judith C. Chavez, Dr. Miguela B. Napiere, and Dr. Revina O. Mendoza – for their inspiring teaching and constructive critique from the beginning to the end of this study;

To her parents, who supported, believed, and pushed her to continue this educational endeavor providing emotional, spiritual and financial support;

To her loving and supportive fiancée, for his unmeasurable understanding and selfless support in driving her back and forth from Agusan del Sur to Cagayan de Oro City;

To her friends and colleagues for their encouragement during every breakdown and for extending their helping hand in every work-related disruption;

The graduate studies' faculty and staff of Lourdes College for meeting all inquiries and requests throughout her educational path;

The Division of Agusan del Sur most importantly the IPED multi-grade schools as research participants, and school administrators for their valuable assistance, for sparing their time and their cooperation, and for being a part of this study.

REFERENCES

- Brackett, M. A., Rivers, S. E., Reyes, M. R., & Salovey, P. (2019). *Emotional intelligence: Implications for personal, social, academic, and workplace success*. Yale University Press.
- CASEL. (2019). What is SEL? Collaborative for Academic, Social, and Emotional Learning. <https://casel.org/what-is-sel/>
- Collie, R. J., Martin, A. J., & Frydenberg, E. (2022). Teachers' social and emotional competence: Links with well-being and instructional quality. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 109, 103557.
- Gebre, Z. A., Demissie, M. M., & Yimer, B. M. (2025). The impact of teacher socio-emotional competence on student engagement: a meta-analysis. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 16, 1526371.
- Goldstein, M. L. (2023). *Perceptions of Elementary School Teachers on the Implementation of a Social Emotional Learning Curriculum: A Case Study* (Doctoral dissertation, Northcentral University).
- Jones, D. E., Greenberg, M. T., & Crowley, M. (2020). Promoting social-emotional competence in early childhood classrooms: Building resilience in young learners. *Early Education and Development*, 31(2), 213-235. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10409289.2020.1718349>
- Lavigne, A. L., Ryan, J., & Allison, B. (2021). Exploring teachers' beliefs about SEL: Implications for practice and policy. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 113(4), 725-740.
- McClelland, M. M., Tominey, S. L., Schmitt, S. A., & Duncan, R. (2017). SEL interventions in early childhood. *The Future of Children*, 27(1), 33–47.
- Roberts, J. (2022). *Teachers' perceptions implementing social and emotional learning and the impact on students* [Doctoral dissertation, Liberty University]. Liberty University Digital Commons.
- Schonert-Reichl, K. A. (2023). *Social and Emotional Learning in schools: Current*

- research and future directions. *Educational Psychologist*, 58(2), 89-104.
- Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes*. Harvard University Press.
- White, R. G., & Van Der Boor, C. (2020). Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic and initial period of lockdown on the mental health and well-being of adults in the UK. *BJPsych open*, 6(5), e90.
- Zins, J. E., Weissberg, R. P., Wang, M. C., & Walberg, H. J. (Eds.). (2020). *Building Academic success on social and emotional learning: What does the research say?* Teachers College Press.